

README -- Dataset for "A latitudinal study of insolation on geometric forms"

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Overview

This dataset contains computed m-index values and supporting data for a study of solar irradiation on geometric building forms across nine locations from 6°N to 64°N. The m-index ($m = G/G_0$) is the ratio of mean annual irradiation on the building envelope to horizontal irradiation at the same location. All irradiation data were retrieved from PVGIS v5.3 (https://re.jrc.ec.europa.eu/pvg_tools/en/).

Files

m & u ALL.xlsx Annual m-index values for 92 building forms at nine study locations (Reykjavik, Aarhus, London, Bologna, Athens, Alexandria, Riyadh, Dakar, Lagos). Columns per location: form code, form type, B/F ratio, annual horizontal irradiation G_0 (kWh/m²/yr), annual envelope mean irradiation G (kWh/m²/yr), annual m-index (%), u-coefficient. Colour coding uses a single scale common to all nine locations.

ALL calc REY.xlsx / ALL calc ATH.xlsx / ALL calc LAG.xlsx Monthly m-index values for all 92 forms at three representative locations: Reykjavik (64°N), Athens (38°N) and Lagos (6°N). Columns: form code, form type, B/F ratio, monthly m-index Jan--Dec (%), annual m-index (%), u-coefficient. Colour coding uses an independent scale per location to reveal internal seasonal structure.

Validation.xlsx Validation results for 22 additional locations across four continents. Three square box forms tested per location (B/F = 0.500, 0.200, 0.059). Columns: region, city, code, latitude, form, B/F, G_S , G_{EW} , G_N , G_H , m_{actual} , m_{linear} , error_linear (%), $m_{quadratic}$, error_quadratic (%). Includes regional and overall MAE summaries.

pvgis_batch_v18.gs Google Apps Script (JavaScript) for batch retrieval and computation of monthly and annual irradiation data from PVGIS v5.3 for the nine study locations and 92 form variants. Requires a Google Sheets spreadsheet to run. Computes m-index, u-coefficient, and monthly profiles for each form.

pvgis_validate_global_v6.gs Google Apps Script (JavaScript) for validation of the $u(\phi)$ formula at 22 additional locations plus a same-latitude group of four locations at ~38°N. Computes m_{actual} from PVGIS data and compares with m_{linear} and $m_{quadratic}$ predictions. Fixes a display bug present in v4 where G_N and G_S columns were swapped (m_{actual} computation was unaffected).

Form types and codes

Seven form types are included: Box (B, 40 variants), Pitched roof (R, 30 variants), Pyramid (P, 5 variants), Cone (K, 5 variants), Cylinder (C, 5 variants), Vault (V, 6 variants), Hemisphere (H, 1 variant). Total: 92 forms. Form codes consist of a letter (type) and number (variant index).

Radiation databases

PVGIS-SARAH3: Lagos, Dakar, Riyadh, Alexandria, Athens, Bologna. PVGIS-ERA5: London, Aarhus, Reykjavik (SARAH3 accuracy reduced above ~55°N). Ground albedo: 0.20 for all locations. Terrain horizon shading not applied.

Formulas

m-index: $m = G/G_0$

Linear relationship: $m = u \cdot (B/F - 1) + 1$

Per-form u-coefficient: $u = (m - 1)/(B/F - 1)$

Linear $u(\phi)$: $u = 0.684 - 0.00557 \cdot \phi$ ($R^2 = 0.889$)

Quadratic $u(\phi)$: $u = 0.591 + 0.0017 \cdot \phi - 0.0001 \cdot \phi^2$ ($R^2 = 0.974$)

Climate classifications

Köppen-Geiger classifications per Beck et al. (2023): High-resolution (1 km) Köppen-Geiger maps for 1901--2099 based on constrained CMIP6 projections. Scientific Data, 10, 724. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02549-6>

Contact

For questions about the dataset or scripts, contact the corresponding author via the journal.